

PROBLEMS OF MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: this article discusses the problems, necessity, and relevance of school management today.

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Management activity, like any activity, performs its tasks based on a number of principles. In the pedagogical literature, special emphasis is placed on determining the principles that serve as the basis for the management of the educational system based on the tasks performed by them (planning, organization and control).

An internal work style plan implemented by managers may include the following issues:

1. Implementation of the plan for all indicators of educational institutions.
2. The state of educational work.
3. Educational activities carried out outside of studies and studies.
4. Work with the public and partner organizations in the institution.
5. The issue of knowledge and performance of pedagogic staff in institutions.
6. The state of keeping the institution's documents.
7. Activities of student youth organizations.
8. Financial affairs of the institution.
9. Institution, family and public cooperation.
10. Work of group leaders and other issues.[1]

Currently, the issue of providing highly qualified and knowledgeable specialists to the public education system of our country is being solved in the system of educational institutions. Taking into account the developing demand and future of the higher education system, professors and teachers of higher educational institutions are mainly required to meet four conditions:

1. Excellent knowledge of one's subject.
2. Love your profession with all your heart.
3. To instill in students a love for science.
4. To organize practical work based on the requirements of the current period and to have deep knowledge.[2]

It is clear from it that the goal is to further improve the quality of specialists, to educate them as creative thinkers and enterprising specialists. This, in turn, requires a fundamental improvement of education for students and providing them with education at the level of modern requirements.

As soon as students step into educational institutions, they master the secrets of the sciences in their chosen field with patience and perseverance. To treat the person with special respect in the management of the educational system, to trust him/her, to achieve the level of subject-to-subject relationship in pedagogical activities, to protect the rights and interests of the student and teacher, to use their talents and professional creation of conditions for free manifestation of skills means the essence of management based on the principle of humanity.

Systematicity and uniformity of management. Based on the systematic approach to the management of the educational institution, the leader has a clear idea of the educational institution as a whole system and its characteristics.

1. The first sign of the system is its unity and the ability to divide it into parts and components.

2. The second sign indicates the presence of the internal structure of the system.

3. The third sign is the ability to integrate the system. [3]

As each component of the system has its own quality, a new integrability quality of the system is formed through interaction. The fourth sign is the close connection of educational institutions with the external environment. Because educational institutions adapt to the external environment, rebuild this educational process and subjugate the external environment to achieve their goals. Systematicity and uniformity in management ensures interaction and communication between the leader and the pedagogical team, prevents one-sided management. Rational combination of centralized and decentralized management. When the centralization of management is more than necessary, administrative management will certainly increase. This situation leads to not taking into account the needs, demands and wishes of teachers and students, and to spending unnecessary work and time on the part of leaders and teachers. Also, if decentralization is given too much attention, the activity of the pedagogical system will slow down. Harmonization of centralization and decentralization in management within the educational institution focuses the activities of administrative and public management leaders in the interest of the community and creates conditions for making decisions at the level of professional competence. The principle of the unity of single administration and

public management is aimed at preventing single administration in the management of the pedagogical process. It is very important to draw reasonable conclusions based on the experience and knowledge of students, comparing different views in management activities. Collegial resolution of tasks does not eliminate the responsibility of each team member.

In turn, the monopoly has its own characteristics. Autonomy ensures discipline, the scope of authority and its implementation in the pedagogical process, if a collegial approach to decision-making is preferable, it is preferable to submit to autonomy in ensuring the execution of the decision. The public character of the management of the educational system creates conditions for the implementation of this principle. Objectivity and completeness of information in the management of the educational system. The effectiveness of the management of the educational system depends on the accuracy and completeness of the information. If the information is accurate, complete or too much, it will lead to confusion in decision-making.

In conclusion, it should be noted that we collect information about students' learning during the educational process, but we pay attention to their interests, behavior, and direction as individuals. That is why many deviations are observed in the process of education. The head of the educational institution also acts as a manager in his/her activities.

Therefore, he should be able to widely use observation, questionnaire, test, instructional and methodical materials in his work. The administration of the educational institution should pay special attention to the development of information management technology within the school and its implementation in the educational process. Effective use of information in the management process helps the successful implementation of the activity of the educational institution. The information used in the management of the educational institution is different. The formation of the information fund and its intensive use increases the scientific organization of management work. The effectiveness of the management of the educational institution depends on the deep knowledge of the pedagogical analysis methodology of both the leader and the teachers. If the pedagogic process is not properly analyzed at the professional level in time, mutual misunderstanding and mistrust will arise among the team. The basis of any pedagogical process management is goal setting and planning. The purpose of management activity is to determine the general direction, content, form and methods of work. So, the goal is the basis of the plan. After determining the main goal in management, an additional goal is set to achieve it. Management planning of an educational institution is decision-making in

accordance with the program goals set on the basis of pedagogical analysis. Such decisions can be made by analyzing data for a certain period of time or after completing the final work. The following three main forms of planning are used in the practice of educational institution management: long-term (perspective); annual; final.[4]

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